

Learning the Exciton Properties of Azo-dyes

Sergi Vela, Alberto Fabrizio, Ksenia R. Briling and Clémence Corminboeuf*

*Institute of Chemical Sciences and Engineering, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL),
Laboratory for Computational Molecular Design, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland*

Abstract

The *ab initio* determination of electronic excited state (ES) properties is the cornerstone of theoretical photochemistry. Yet, traditional ES methods become impractical when applied to fairly large molecules, or when used on thousands of systems. Machine Learning (ML) techniques have demonstrated their accuracy at retrieving ES properties of large molecular databases at a reduced computational cost. For these applications, non-linear algorithms tend to be specialized in targeting individual properties. Learning fundamental quantum objects potentially represents a more efficient, yet complex, alternative as a variety of molecular properties could be extracted through post-processing. Herein, we report a general framework able to learn three fundamental objects: the hole and particle densities, as well as the transition density. We demonstrate the advantages of targeting those outputs and apply our predictions to obtain properties, including the state character and the exciton topological descriptors, for the two bands ($n\pi^*$ and $\pi\pi^*$) of 3427 azoheteroarene photoswitches.

The interaction of light with molecules plays a pivotal role in natural and life sciences (bioimaging,¹ photopharmacology², photosynthesis³), technology (solar cells,⁴ photovoltaics⁵⁻⁷) and chemistry (synthesis, motors⁸). Computationally, this interaction is typically investigated through the analysis of the electronic excited states (ES) wave-function,^{9, 10} which is composed (within the linear response approximation) of the ground-state molecular orbitals and the Transition Density Matrix (TDM).¹¹ The TDM has become a fundamental object in the study of photo-induced processes, as it encodes the exciton densities, and can easily be analyzed in an automated-friendly manner,¹²⁻¹⁷ which simplifies the study of large databases,^{18, 19} and the identification of trends connecting the states character with its properties.^{13, 20}

Nonetheless, the TDM is a rather poor object to be represented in real-space (6-dimensional) and its sign is only conventionally defined, but otherwise arbitrary.²¹ The closest quantum chemical objects that retain the information of the TDM, while improving on its representability, are the hole and particle densities [$\rho_H(\mathbf{r})$ and $\rho_P(\mathbf{r})$]. These encode the separate probability distribution of the quasi-particles (hole and particle) upon electronic transition, and are defined in Eq. 1, where $\chi_{p/q}(\mathbf{r})$ and $T^{H/P}$ are the atomic orbitals and the Hole/Particle density matrix in AO-basis, respectively. Within the Tamm-Dancoff approximation,²² these two fields are readily obtained from the TDM by multiplication with its adjoint for the hole ($T^H = X \cdot X^\dagger$) and vice versa for the particle ($T^P = X^\dagger \cdot X$). Derived from the same quantum chemical objects, $\rho_H(\mathbf{r})$ and $\rho_P(\mathbf{r})$ contain the same information as the TDM with the sole exception of the Hole-Particle correlation.

Conversely, they are readily representable in real-space, and strictly positive-defined for all molecules.

$$\rho_{H/P}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{pq} T_{qp}^{H/P} \chi_p(\mathbf{r}) \chi_q(\mathbf{r}) \approx \sum_i c_i \phi_i(\mathbf{r}) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Borrowing the classification of excited state properties by Westermayr and Marquetand,²³ the hole and particle densities could be considered as primary outputs, as they describe the most fundamental quantum chemical property: the spatial distribution of (quasi-) particles. From this information, it is, in principle, possible to determine any other molecular quantity by adequate post-processing. However, the challenge lies in building a non-linear regression model able to provide a one-to-one mapping between the structural -and chemical- composition of a molecule, and its quasi-particle densities, $\rho_H(\mathbf{r})$ and $\rho_P(\mathbf{r})$. One of the possibilities leverages the well-established practice of decomposing real-space scalar fields into a weighted sum (c_i in Eq. 1) of local atomic contributions using an atom-centered basis set ($\phi_i(\mathbf{r})$ in Eq. 1).^{24, 25} In combination with symmetry-adapted (SA) machine learning techniques, such as the SA-Gaussian Process Regression (SA-GPR), this strategy is capable of encoding the complex rotation symmetries of real-space fields.

Scheme 1. Representation of the azo-dye structure, with the fragment nomenclature (R_n)

This framework, already described in the literature,^{23, 24} has been used by some of us to accurately predict ground-state densities,²⁶ and is here adapted (see Section S3.1) for the prediction of $\rho_H(\mathbf{r})$ and $\rho_P(\mathbf{r})$ of excited states.

Herein, we highlight (i) the usefulness of this ML model in a series of applications, and (ii) its complexity due to the nature of the targeted fields. Leveraging on our previous experience in azo-heteroarenes,^{20, 27, 28} we constructed a database of 3427 dyes, which maximizes the chemical diversity of the substituents and their impact on the character of the electronic transition (see computational details). The full database was randomly divided into a training set (1300 molecules), a test set (200), and an out-of-sample set (1927). Azo-dyes are one of the most-widespread molecular scaffolds in photochemistry (see Table S1).²⁹⁻³¹ They undergo photoisomerization after irradiation of either of their *productive* bands, namely a dark $n\pi^*$, and a bright $\pi\pi^*$. These bands are common in all azo-dyes, and the modulation of its character has a significant impact on its optical properties,²⁰ and on the photo-isomerization mechanism, dynamics, and quantum yield.²⁸ From a design perspective, it has been, for instance, demonstrated that *push-pull* photoswitches may represent an appealing alternative to improve the photoisomerization quantum yields.^{28, 30, 32} The azo-dyes in our database result from the combination of the azo moiety (in its E-isomer) with four other fragments, labelled R_{1-4} (see Scheme 1). In those systems, the $n\pi^*$ transition is local and not prone to changes, but the $\pi\pi^*$ one can be significantly tuned upon substitution (see Section S2), and thus poses a greater challenge to ML methods. Overall, the combination of a dark and rather constant $n\pi^*$ state, together with a bright and variable $\pi\pi^*$ state, represents an excellent test-bed to assess the generality of the learning framework and its post-processing.

Figure 1. (top) Learning Curves associated with the Hole and Particle of the *productive* $n\pi^*$ and $\pi\pi^*$ states. For comparison, the transition density (TD) of the $\pi\pi^*$ band, and the ground state density are also shown. The absolute error in the total fields is defined in Eq. 2, and is evaluated on randomly-selected 200 test-set molecules. (below) Particle distribution of the $\pi\pi^*$ state for one representative compound in the

dataset (isovalue=0.001). The *ab initio* particle density (left), and the prediction error (right) are reported in the bottom.

The learning of the two bands is first assessed through the learning curves of the two targeted fields $[\rho_{H/P}(\mathbf{r})]$ for the $n\pi^*$ and $\pi\pi^*$ states (Figure 1). The absolute error is defined as the electrostatic self-repulsion of the difference between the predicted $[\rho^{ML}(\mathbf{r})]$ and reference (*i.e.*, *ab initio*) $[\rho^{ref}(\mathbf{r})]$ densities. For completeness, we report also two different relative metrics, and the visual comparison of the learning curve for one compound (see Section S3). From the curves in Figure 1, it is evident that the accuracy of our framework differs for each of the targeted states. The learning exercise is easier on the $n\pi^*$ than on the $\pi\pi^*$ state, for which the hole density is especially difficult to learn, as anticipated from its greater variability with chemical substitution.

$$Abs. Err. = \left(\rho^{ML}(\mathbf{r}_1) - \rho^{ref}(\mathbf{r}_1) \right) \frac{1}{r_{12}} \left| \rho^{ML}(\mathbf{r}_2) - \rho^{ref}(\mathbf{r}_2) \right| \text{ Eq. 2}$$

To assess the impact of the prediction errors on concrete quantum chemical applications, we first apply the predicted $\rho_{H/P}(\mathbf{r})$ to describe the character of the $n\pi^*$ and $\pi\pi^*$ states. To do so, we decompose the $\rho_{H/P}(\mathbf{r})$ into the five fragments described in Scheme 1 using the Hirshfeld partitioning scheme.³³ For the 200 test set molecules, the resulting $H_{R_1-R_4}$ and $P_{R_1-R_4}$ are then compared to the *ab-initio* counterparts obtained from the charge-transfer values Ω_{AB} (see computational details). The results show that the $n\pi^*$ band is perfectly captured by our protocol, with the error in $X_{R_1-R_4}$ ($X = H, P$) being typically smaller than 1% when learned on the full training set (see Figure S3.3). The accuracy of the fragment-based Hirshfeld contributions diminish for the $\pi\pi^*$ band (3-6% error) but to a much smaller extent than the absolute prediction error (Figure 1). This is highly encouraging for the prospect of extracting chemically-relevant information from the learned densities.

Figure 2. Evolution of the learning of (top) $P_{AZO}^{n\pi^*}$ and (bottom) $H_{R_1}^{n\pi^*}$ for the 200 molecules included in the test set, upon increasing the training set size (from 325 to 1300 molecules).

Also shown in inset the evolution of the MAE associated with each distribution (from left to right).

One representative example of the $X_{R_1-R_4}$ learning for each of the two states are the evolution of $P_{AZO}^{n\pi^*}$ and $H_{R_1}^{\pi\pi^*}$, shown in Figure 2. While the former improves significantly in larger training sets, the latter is only slightly better, as expected from the learning curves (see Figure 1). The predictions correlate very well with the *ab initio* values when the density amplitudes ($X_{R_1-R_4}^{\pi\pi^*}$) are small on each fragment (*i.e.*, the field is delocalized). In contrast, the model tends to underestimate the fragment contributions if the field is mainly localized on a particular fragment. This trend appears graphically as a flatter correlation in Figure 2, and implies a bias of our model towards a more uniform spread of the densities. The fact that the $\pi\pi^*$ hole densities are predicted to be more delocalized than the *ab initio* reference (see section S2) illustrates an important challenge of learning electronic excitations; two molecules with a nearly identical structure and composition (excluding some peripheral substitutions) may have dramatically different $\rho_{H/P}(\mathbf{r})$ distributions. That is, the contribution of a given molecular fragment ($X_{R_1-R_4}$) to the total field is not only dictated by its immediate environment, but can be significantly altered by the non-additive presence of farther substituents. To cope with this difficulty, the ML model averages out the field over all molecular fragments while minimizing the overall error, effectively spreading the predicted Hole and Particle densities. The relationship between local chemical substitutions and prediction error is even more evident when analyzing of the correlation between the accuracy of the $\pi\pi^*$ -Hole state and the π -conjugation of the R₃ and R₄ fragments (Section S4).

The predicted $\rho_{H/P}(\mathbf{r})$ can also be used to characterize the exciton using topological descriptors such as the exciton distance (d_{HP}),¹⁵ the Hole and Particle size (σ_H , and σ_P),¹⁴ or the transition dipole moment (μ_0) (see Figure 3). The predicted d_{HP} values capture the *ab-initio* trends for both states. The agreement is indeed quantitative for the more localized $n\pi^*$ state, with a MAE of 0.1 Bohr. However, for the $\pi\pi^*$ state the artificial delocalization induced by the ML model leads to the underestimation of the predicted d_{HP} by about 50%, and to a slightly larger σ_H . Nevertheless, the prediction correctly characterizes the delocalized π vs. the localized n orbital that dominates the Hole (σ_H), as well as the comparable particle size (σ_P) of both states, which involve excitations to the same π^* orbital localized in -and around- the azo group. Finally, the transition dipole moment (μ),³⁴ a key ingredient to retrieve

the oscillator strength of electronic excitations, is captured with moderately-good accuracy for the bright $\pi\pi^*$ band.

Figure 3. Comparison of predicted and *ab-initio* topological descriptors for the (red) $n\pi^*$ and (blue) $\pi\pi^*$ states. (a-b) show the Hole-Particle distance d_{HP} , (c) the norm of the transition dipole moment of the $\pi\pi^*$ state $|\mu|$, and (d) the Hole and (e) Particle size, $\sigma_{H/P}$. All values are given in Bohr.

We now discuss the predictive potential of the model for the more tunable $\pi\pi^*$ state (see Section S6 for $n\pi^*$ state) with the prospect of identifying those with the largest *push-pull* signature. In particular, we analyze whether the method is able to capture the interplay between the chemical composition and the states character. From previous work,²⁰ it is known that the character of the $\pi\pi^*$ band depends on (i) the π -conjugation length, and on (ii) the electronic properties of the fragments, in a way that donor (acceptor) fragments tend to contribute more to the particle (hole). An analysis of the predicted $\rho_{H/P}(\mathbf{r})$ for the out-of-sample set (1927 molecules *new* to the ML model) reveals that the two points are correctly captured by the model. The Hole contribution of the outer R₃ fragment (see Scheme 1) is larger when those are π -conjugated, and even more so when they are also good donors, such as in the case of thiazine (see Figure 4). A similar correlation is found between the hole and particle contribution of R₂ fragments and their electronic properties. Examples are tetrazole and adenine. The former is both a bad donor and a bad acceptor and, accordingly, the model ascribes it the smallest hole and particle density, while the latter is the best R₂ acceptor and, as such, is associated with the largest particle contribution (see Section S5). The fact that the model can capture the contrasting chemistry of the fragments means that it can describe correctly the effects of π -conjugation and electronic character on $\rho_{H/P}(\mathbf{r})$. This information is especially relevant because it will have consequences on the overall photoswitch *push-pull* character and properties (*e.g.*, larger *push-pull* character leads to a larger quantum yield).^{28, 30, 32}

Figure 4. Correlation between predicted excited-state character and chemical composition in the azo-dyes included in the out-of-sample set. Each point represents a compound, and the color code corresponds to the predicted hole in fragment R_3 . Spatial proximity of points in the xy-plane reflects their similarity in structure and composition. A third chemically-intuitive dimension (z axis) is imposed to separate those compounds where the R_3 fragment is a π -conjugated system (middle set) from the others (back). In front, compounds with thiazine as R_3 . This data, as well as all other descriptor predictions for the out-of-sample set, can be found as an interactive app in <https://vfb21.herokuapp.com/>.

In summary, we report the learning of three fundamental outputs of an excited state computation, the real-space Hole and Particle distributions $[\rho_{H/P}(\mathbf{r})]$ as well as the transition density and we demonstrate their applicability to predict the character, and representative topological properties of the two *productive* excitations of azo-based photoswitches. The proposed ML framework is able to overcome the technical challenges associated with the learning of scalar fields, and offers an outstanding (for the $n\pi^*$ state) or moderate ($\pi\pi^*$ state) accuracy depending on the correlation between the chemical substitution and the spatial extent of the density response. The most problematic systems are those where changes in peripheral substituents modify entirely the shape and the distribution of the densities. In these cases, future work must be devoted to encode the potential non-local response of electronic excitations in the molecular representation to changes in substituents, without limiting the scalability and transferability of the model.²⁴⁻²⁶ The framework presented in this work has been trained on LR-TDDFT quality hole and particle fields, but no change in its architecture would be required for future applications targeting higher-level quantum chemical methods, such as CASSCF or EOM-CC. Finally, we demonstrate that the model is sufficiently flexible to be applied to organize a larger out-of-sample database of 1927 azo-dyes based on the excited states character of the two bands and extract chemically relevant information such as the extent of *push-pull* signature. Overall, all these characteristics combined make the proposed framework an appealing alternative to traditional quantum-chemistry methods for

the large-scale characterization of the ES character and derived properties as well as for the exploration of larger molecules as demonstrated in the case of the ground state electron density.²⁴⁻²⁶

Computational Methods

A database of 3427 azoheteroarenes has been generated, resulting from the combination of the azo moiety with four other fragments, labelled R_{1-4} (see Section S1). These fragments are built and handled in the SMILES notation,³⁵ and put together using local scripts. The conversion from SMILES to 3D coordinates is then performed with OpenBabel version 2.4.136, which includes a conformational search and a MMFF94 force field optimization.³⁶ The resulting geometries are further optimized at the GFN2-DFTB level using the xtb code.^{37, 38} Based on previous benchmarks,²⁰ the linear-response LR-TDDFT (with TDA approximation^{22, 39}) computations were then performed at the ω B97X-D^{40, 41}/def2-SVP level. The lowest 10 singlet states were systematically computed. The identification of the productive states within the excited state manifold (see Section S2), as well as their analysis, was carried out using charge-transfer matrices extracted from Gaussian 09 outputs using *cclib* (for parsing),⁴² and the analysis of the transition density matrix provided in TheoDOR version 1.7.1.^{12, 43}

The database was randomly divided into a training set (1300 molecules), a test set (200 molecules) and an out-of-sample set (1927 molecules). The computation of basis set projection and Coulomb integrals for all the fields included in this work was performed with PySCF.^{44, 45} The Coulomb metric was used both for the basis set decomposition with cc-pVQZ-JKFIT⁴⁶, and for the loss function of the machine learning model (see section S3).⁴⁷ The tensorial λ -SOAP kernels⁴⁸ were computed using an environment cutoff of 3 Å, Gaussian smearing of 0.3 Å, angular cutoff 6, radial cutoff 8, and environmental kernel exponent $\zeta=2$. Sparse regression was performed with a subset of $M=1000$ reference environments to reduce the dimensionality of the regression problem. The regularization parameter η was set to 10^{-6} .

Supporting Information. Definition of the fragment library, details concerning the construction of the dataset including the identification of the productive $n\pi^*$ and $\text{p}\pi\pi^*$ states, details on the machine learning framework, an in depth comparison between predicted and ab-initio topological descriptors, the analysis of the $\pi\pi^*$ and $n\pi^*$ character of the out-of-sample set.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest. All relevant data and software will be made available upon

publication in dedicated Materials Cloud repository. Interactive plots of the out-of-sample set data (including 1927 molecules) are available as an Heroku deployed app (<https://vfb21.herokuapp.com/>). A Github repository is also available (github.com/lcmd-epfl/azo-xcite-tools), with details to reproduce the excited state computations, field modifications, and computation of the excited state descriptors. All the raw data have been deposited in a Materials Cloud repository.

Acknowledgements

S.V and A.F. acknowledge funding from the National Centre of Competence in Research (NCCR) “Materials’ Revolution: Computational Design and Discovery of Novel Materials (MARVEL)” of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), and K.R.B. of the European Research Council (ERC, G.A. #817977). The authors also acknowledge support from EPFL, and help from R. Fabregat at setting the Heroku app and generating graphical material.

References

1. Dommaschk, M.; Peters, M.; Gutzeit, F.; Schütt, C.; Näther, C.; Sönnichsen, F. D.; Tiwari, S.; Riedel, C.; Boretius, S.; Herges, R. Photoswitchable Magnetic Resonance Imaging Contrast by Improved Light-Driven Coordination-Induced Spin State Switch. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 7552-7555.
2. Velema, W. A.; Szymanski, W.; Feringa, B. L. Photopharmacology: Beyond Proof of Principle. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 2178-2191.
3. Feher, G.; Allen, J. P.; Okamura, M. Y.; Rees, D. C. Structure and Function of Bacterial Photosynthetic Reaction Centres. *Nature* **1989**, *339*, 111-116.
4. O'Regan, B.; Grätzel, M. A Low-Cost, High-Efficiency Solar Cell Based on Dye-Sensitized Colloidal TiO₂ Films. *Nature* **1991**, *353*, 737-740.
5. Casanova, D. Theoretical Modeling of Singlet Fission. *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 7164-7207.
6. Hedley, G. J.; Ruseckas, A.; Samuel, I. D. W. Light Harvesting for Organic Photovoltaics. *Chem. Rev.* **2017**, *117*, 796-837.
7. Ullrich, T.; Munz, D.; Guldi, D. M. Unconventional Singlet Fission Materials. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2021**, *50*, 3485-3518.
8. Balzani, V.; Credi, A.; Venturi, M. Light Powered Molecular Machines. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2009**, *38*, 1542-1550.
9. Curchod, B. F. E.; Martínez, T. J. Ab Initio Nonadiabatic Quantum Molecular Dynamics. *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 3305-3336.
10. Curutchet, C.; Mennucci, B. Quantum Chemical Studies of Light Harvesting. *Chem. Rev.* **2017**, *117*, 294-343.
11. Dreuw, A.; Head-Gordon, M. Single-Reference Ab Initio Methods for the Calculation of Excited States of Large Molecules. *Chem. Rev.* **2005**, *105*, 4009-4037.
12. Plasser, F.; Lischka, H. Analysis of Excitonic and Charge Transfer Interactions from Quantum Chemical Calculations. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2012**, *8*, 2777-2789.
13. Mai, S.; Plasser, F.; Dorn, J.; Fumanal, M.; Daniel, C.; González, L. Quantitative Wave Function Analysis for Excited States of Transition Metal Complexes. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *361*, 74-97.
14. Plasser, F.; Thomitzni, B.; Bäßler, S. A.; Wenzel, J.; Rehn, D. R.; Wormit, M.; Dreuw, A. Statistical Analysis of Electronic Excitation Processes: Spatial Location, Compactness, Charge Transfer, and Electron-Hole Correlation. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2015**, *36*, 1609-1620.
15. Mewes, S. A.; Dreuw, A. Density-Based Descriptors and Exciton Analyses for Visualizing and Understanding the Electronic Structure of Excited States. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2019**, *21*, 2843-2856.
16. Mewes, S. A.; Mewes, J.-M.; Dreuw, A.; Plasser, F. Excitons in Poly(Para Phenylene Vinylene): A Quantum-Chemical Perspective Based on High-Level Ab Initio Calculations. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2016**, *18*, 2548-2563.
17. Hirose, D.; Noguchi, Y.; Sugino, O. Quantitative Characterization of Exciton from Gw+Bethe-Salpeter Calculation. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2017**, *146*, 044303.
18. Blaskovits, J. T.; Fumanal, M.; Vela, S.; Corminboeuf, C. Designing Singlet Fission Candidates from Donor-Acceptor Copolymers. *Chem. Mater.* **2020**, *32*, 6515-6524.
19. Blaskovits, J. T.; Fumanal, M.; Vela, S.; Fabregat, R.; Corminboeuf, C. Identifying the Trade-Off between Intramolecular Singlet Fission Requirements in Donor-Acceptor Copolymers. *Chem. Mater.* **2021**, *33*, 2567-2575.
20. Vela, S.; Krüger, C.; Corminboeuf, C. Exploring Chemical Space in the Search for Improved Azoheteroarene-Based Photoswitches. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2019**, *21*, 20782-20790.
21. Westermayr, J.; Gastegger, M.; Menger, M. F. S. J.; Mai, S.; González, L.; Marquetand, P. Machine Learning Enables Long Time Scale Molecular Photodynamics Simulations. *Chem. Sci.* **2019**, *10*, 8100-8107.
22. Hirata, S.; Head-Gordon, M. Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory within the Tamm-Dancoff Approximation. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1999**, *314*, 291-299.
23. Westermayr, J.; Marquetand, P. Machine Learning for Electronically Excited States of Molecules. *Chem. Rev.* **2020**.
24. Grisafi, A.; Fabrizio, A.; Meyer, B.; Wilkins, D. M.; Corminboeuf, C.; Ceriotti, M. Transferable Machine-Learning Model of the Electron Density. *ACS Cent. Sci.* **2019**, *5*, 57-64.
25. Fabrizio, A.; Grisafi, A.; Meyer, B.; Ceriotti, M.; Corminboeuf, C. Electron Density Learning of Non-Covalent Systems. *Chem. Sci.* **2019**, *10*, 9424-9432.
26. Fabrizio, A.; Briling, K. R.; Girardier, D. D.; Corminboeuf, C. Learning on-Top: Regressing the on-Top Pair Density for Real-Space Visualization of Electron Correlation. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2020**, *153*, 204111.
27. Vela, S.; Scheidegger, A.; Fabregat, R.; Corminboeuf, C. Tuning the Thermal Stability and Photoisomerization of Azoheteroarenes through Macrocyclic Strain. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2021**, *27*, 419-426.
28. Vela, S.; Corminboeuf, C. The Photoisomerization Pathway(S) of Push-Pull Phenylazoheteroarenes. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2020**, *26*, 14724-14729.
29. Crespi, S.; Simeth, N. A.; König, B. Heteroaryl Azo Dyes as Molecular Photoswitches. *Nat. Rev. Chem.* **2019**, *3*, 133-146.
30. Bandara, H. M. D.; Burdette, S. C. Photoisomerization in Different Classes of Azobenzene. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2012**, *41*, 1809-1825.
31. Beharry, A. A.; Woolley, G. A. Azobenzene Photoswitches for Biomolecules. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2011**, *40*, 4422-4437.
32. Aleotti, F.; Nenov, A.; Salvigni, L.; Bonfanti, M.; El-Tahawy, M. M.; Giunchi, A.; Gentile, M.; Spallacci, C.; Ventimiglia, A.; Cirillo, G.; Montali, L.; Scurti, S.; Garavelli, M.; Conti, I. Spectral Tuning and Photoisomerization Efficiency in Push-Pull Azobenzenes: Designing Principles. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2020**, *124*, 9513-9523.
33. Hirshfeld, F. Difference Densities by Least-Squares Refinement: Fumaramic Acid. *Acta Crystallogr., Sect. B* **1971**, *27*, 769-781.

34. Notice that the transition dipole moment is indeed extracted from the learned TD, as described in Section 3.2
35. Weininger, D. Smiles, a Chemical Language and Information System. 1. Introduction to Methodology and Encoding Rules. *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.* **1988**, *28*, 31-36.
36. O'Boyle, N. M.; Banck, M.; James, C. A.; Morley, C.; Vandermeersch, T.; Hutchison, G. R. Open Babel: An Open Chemical Toolbox. *J. Cheminformatics* **2011**, *3*, 33.
37. Bannwarth, C.; Ehlert, S.; Grimme, S. Gfn2-Xtb—an Accurate and Broadly Parametrized Self-Consistent Tight-Binding Quantum Chemical Method with Multipole Electrostatics and Density-Dependent Dispersion Contributions. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2019**, *15*, 1652-1671.
38. Bannwarth, C.; Caldeweyher, E.; Ehlert, S.; Hansen, A.; Pracht, P.; Seibert, J.; Spicher, S.; Grimme, S. Extended Tight-Binding Quantum Chemistry Methods. *WIREs Comput. Mol. Sci.* **2021**, *11*, e1493.
39. Casida, M. E.; Gutierrez, F.; Guan, J.; Gadea, F.-X.; Salahub, D.; Daudey, J.-P. Charge-Transfer Correction for Improved Time-Dependent Local Density Approximation Excited-State Potential Energy Curves: Analysis within the Two-Level Model with Illustration for H₂ and LiH. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2000**, *113*, 7062-7071.
40. Chai, J.-D.; Head-Gordon, M. Systematic Optimization of Long-Range Corrected Hybrid Density Functionals. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2008**, *128*, 084106.
41. Chai, J.-D.; Head-Gordon, M. Long-Range Corrected Hybrid Density Functionals with Damped Atom-Atom Dispersion Corrections. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2008**, *10*, 6615-6620.
42. O'boyle, N. M.; Tenderholt, A. L.; Langner, K. M. Cclib: A Library for Package-Independent Computational Chemistry Algorithms. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2008**, *29*, 839-845.
43. Plasser, F. Theodore: A Toolbox for a Detailed and Automated Analysis of Electronic Excited State Computations. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2020**, *152*, 084108.
44. Sun, Q.; Berkelbach, T. C.; Blunt, N. S.; Booth, G. H.; Guo, S.; Li, Z.; Liu, J.; McClain, J. D.; Sayfutyarova, E. R.; Sharma, S.; Wouters, S.; Chan, G. K.-L. Pyscf: The Python-Based Simulations of Chemistry Framework. *WIREs Comput. Mol. Sci.* **2018**, *8*, e1340.
45. Sun, Q. Libcint: An Efficient General Integral Library for Gaussian Basis Functions. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2015**, *36*, 1664-1671.
46. Weigend, F. A Fully Direct Ri-Hf Algorithm: Implementation, Optimised Auxiliary Basis Sets, Demonstration of Accuracy and Efficiency. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2002**, *4*, 4285-4291.
47. Briling, K. R.; Fabrizio, A.; Corminboeuf, C. Impact of Quantum-Chemical Metrics on the Machine Learning Prediction of Electron Density. *arXiv* **2021**, *2104.12457*.
48. Grisafi, A.; Wilkins, D. M.; Csányi, G.; Ceriotti, M. Symmetry-Adapted Machine Learning for Tensorial Properties of Atomistic Systems. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2018**, *120*, 036002.

TOC Graphic:

